

EMP-A

Modelling Decarbonization Pathways in the Power Sector in Ethiopia: A Focus on the Transportation and Residential Cooking Sectors

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Executive Summary

This report analyzes Ethiopia's pathways for decarbonizing its power sector, focusing on transportation and residential cooking. Despite a heavy reliance on hydropower, significant challenges remain, including limited electricity access and rising demand. Ethiopia aims to expand its power generation capacity significantly while reducing greenhouse gas emissions, as outlined in its' Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) targets.

Key research questions explore how electricity demand will evolve due to the adoption of electric vehicles and clean cooking technologies, as well as strategies to meet net-zero emission targets. Using OSeMOSYS, the report examines three scenarios:

1. Business as Usual (BAU): Continuation of current trends
2. Increased EV adoption and Clean Cooking (EV-CC): Anticipates 50% of cooking and transport demand met by electricity by 2050
3. Net Zero (NZ): Aims for a fully decarbonized transport and residential cooking by 2050

By 2050, Ethiopia's transport and residential sectors will require up to a 5.5-fold increase in generation capacity compared to the BAU scenario. While this shift will cut emissions and deliver long-term savings, it will also demand significant upfront investment - an estimated \$9 billion, equivalent to 5.3% of GDP in 2025. To support this transition, we recommend a diversified energy mix, targeted subsidies and loans for electric cookstoves and EVs, and stronger support for private investment through partnerships, feed-in tariffs, and models such as Build-on-Operate (BOO) and Build-on-Transfer (BOT). Future work will focus on refining the data, integrating the model with government policies, applying CLEWs framework for deeper environmental analysis, and incorporating social indicators to capture broader impact.

1. Introduction

Ethiopia's energy system is primarily dominated by hydropower, which accounts for approximately 92% of the country's electricity generation, with wind accounting for 7% [1]. The residential sector consumed 86% of final energy in Ethiopia, followed by transport which consumed 6.2 % in 2022. Despite efforts to expand access, only 55% of Ethiopia's population had access to electricity by 2022 [2]. To address these issues, the Ethiopian government has set ambitious targets for the energy sector. The National Electrification Program 2.0, launched in 2019, aims to achieve universal access by 2030, with 65% of the population connected to the grid and 35% through off-grid solutions [3].

Additionally, the country faces a critical challenge in balancing rising electricity demand with the need for a reliable, affordable, and resilient energy system. Electricity currently accounts for 4% of Ethiopia's total energy supply, with most people still dependent on traditional biomass fuels such as firewood and charcoal for cooking and heating [4]. The current share of population with clean cooking (electric stoves) is 7.5% in 2022. To meet growing demand and improve access, Ethiopia plans to expand its installed power generation capacity from 5.6GW in 2023 to 19.9 GW by 2030, focusing on diversifying its energy mix to include more renewable sources like solar, wind and geothermal [5].

Ethiopia is committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by expanding renewable energy sources, reducing deforestation, and improving energy efficiency. Currently, energy accounts for ~7% of Ethiopia's total GHG emissions, from which the majority is coming from the residential and transport sectors. This presents a key opportunity to shift these sectors to clean electricity to significantly cut national emissions. To support this shift, Ethiopia has made significant strides in clean energy policies, including the 2024 ban on the import of gasoline and diesel vehicles, making it the first country to do so [6], as well as gradual removal of diesel and gasoline fuel subsidies, with full removal expected within a year. While this policy aims to reduce fuel imports and pollution, it also brings challenges, particularly around limited electric vehicles infrastructure and ongoing gaps with electricity access.

This report aims to address several research questions:

1. How will the increase in demand for electric vehicles and clean cooking technologies impact the generation mix?
2. How can Ethiopia meet emissions reduction targets for the power sector while ensuring energy access and system reliability, particularly in light of the projected increase in demand?

We use the OSeMOSYS tool to explore three future scenarios for Ethiopia's power system, described in the next section.

2. Methodology

We compiled historical demand, generation, and resource data from government sources such as the Ethiopian Electric Utility (EEU), the Ministry of Water and Energy, Ethiopian Electric Power (EEP), and international databases such as IEA, UN Stats, and IRENA. Where 2023 data was unavailable, we provided estimations on the data using trends from previous years.

This study uses OSeMOSYS to explore long-term electrification and decarbonization pathways in Ethiopia's power sector, particularly transport and residential cooking. The model follows a bottom-up, linear programming approach that optimizes the energy-technology mix based on cost minimization, subject to constraints such as electricity demand, emissions limits, and technology availability. The model optimizes, allowing both renewable and non-renewable technologies to compete under least cost and availability constraints.

Ethiopia's energy system spans hydropower, wind, solar, geothermal, fossil fuels, and biomass. Key end uses include residential, transport, industrial, and commercial sectors, with biofuel production and fuel imports supplementing energy needs. The reference energy system is presented below:

Reference Energy System (RES)

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Three scenarios were developed to investigate the dynamics of Ethiopia's power system under different policy and demand conditions:

1. **BAU Scenario:** This scenario assumes that historical trends continue, with limited penetration of emerging technologies and organic growth in electricity demand due to population increase and electrification efforts. Hydropower remains dominant, and no emissions constraints are applied
2. **EV-CC Scenario:** This assesses the impact of 50% electrification in the transport and residential cooking sectors. With the ban on imported gasoline and diesel vehicles and a significant push towards electric cooking appliances, this scenario examines the effect of these shifts on electricity demand and required generation
3. **NZ Scenario:** This scenario integrates Ethiopia's targets to reduce GHG emissions, aiming for a fully decarbonized residential and transport sector by 2050.

The scenarios are summarized in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling

Calibrations for the EV-CC and NZ scenarios, starting in 2024, involved adjusting the lower limits and maximum capacities for residential and transport demands, along with capacity factors of the power plants. Additionally, a gradual reduction in gasoline and diesel demand in the transport sector and biomass use in the residential cooking sector was implemented - reaching a 50% reduction vs. BAU in the EV-CC scenario and 100% in the NZ scenario. The reduced demand was then redirected to electricity consumption within both scenarios

3. Results and Discussions

The simulation results of the three scenarios modeled in OSeMOSYS are analyzed based on the following key parameters: Total Installed Capacity, Production by Technology, Annual Investment Cost, and Annual Emissions from all technologies. The data for the first three years (2021-2023) was calibrated by the team, after which the model is free to optimize. The model period spans from 2021 to 2050.

Details are provided in the sub-sections below.

3.1. Total Installed Capacity

Figure 3: Installed Capacity

Ethiopia's power capacity is projected to grow from 5.8 GW in 2021 to 29 GW by 2050, entirely from renewable sources in the BAU scenario. In the EV-CC scenario, the expansion is much faster as we made our calibrations starting in 2030, with capacity reaching nearly 128 GW by 2050, as shown in Figure 3. The NZ scenario goes even further, scaling up to ~ 180 GW by 2050, mainly from solar power, along with additional capacity from geothermal, run-of-river hydro, battery and wind. To meet the rising demand in these scenarios, the model also includes battery storage of about 29 GW in EV-CC and 35 GW in NZ by 2050. Overall, the results show that electrifying transport and cooking will cause a major surge in electricity demand.

3.2. Production by Technology

Figure 4: Production by Technology

Power generation trends align closely with the growth in installed capacity. In the BAU scenario, hydropower continues as the main source, with small additions from wind and solar. Electricity production increases from 68 PJ in 2021 to 229 PJ by 2050 in BAU, as shown in Figure 4 above. In the EV-CC case, more renewables, especially solar and wind and large battery storage, are added to meet the rising demand from electric vehicles and clean cooking, which rises to 910 PJ by 2050 compared to the BAU level of 229 PJ. Under the NZ scenario, generation surges to 1,229 PJ by 2050. Although hydropower and wind dominate electricity generation in the BAU, solar power becomes dominant in the later years of the EV-CC and NZ scenarios. Moreover, the generation of the electricity by geothermal has been shown up in later years of the NZ Scenario to fulfil the increasing demand of electrifying the transport and residential cooking sector by 100%.

3.3. Annualized Investment Cost

Figure 5. Annual Investment Cost

Figure 5 shows that the NZ scenario requires the highest investment, reaching \$9.27 billion by 2050, driven by the large increase in capacity needed to achieve net-zero goals. The EV-CC scenario follows, with investments rising to \$7.64 billion as capacity expands to meet electric vehicle and clean cooking demand. The BAU scenario has the lowest cost at \$2 billion, reflecting lower need for new capacity.

3.4. Annual Emissions

Figure 6. Annual Emissions

According to Figure 6, under the BAU scenario, emissions rise from 16 MtCO₂ in 2021 to over 33 MtCO₂ by 2050, due to increasing energy demand and continued reliance on fossil fuels. In contrast, emissions drop significantly in the EV-CC scenario, from around 16 MtCO₂ in 2021 to about 7 MtCO₂ by 2050 as the transport and residential cooking sectors are gradually electrified, reaching 50% electrification by 2050, with all of the electricity generated from renewable sources. Moreover, the NZ scenario shows a further reduction of the emissions to zero by 2050 in alignment with the scenario's goal of fully decarbonizing the residential and transport sectors.

5. Conclusion & Future Works

Ethiopia's recent ban on fossil fuel vehicles highlights its commitment to accelerating the shift toward electric mobility will aggravate the electricity demand. At the same time, Ethiopia is striving to electrify rural communities and incentivize clean cooking solutions to reduce dependence on traditional fuels like wood and charcoal, which trigger the investment cost for the power generation mix and expansion.

Fully electrifying the transport and residential sector by 2050 (NZ scenario) will require up to a 5.5-fold increase in installed generation capacity vs. BAU. The NZ will cut emissions by 33 MTCO₂ compared to BAU and save money in the long run, but requires large upfront spending of over \$9 billion—about 5.3% of Ethiopia's GDP in 2025. We recommend the government use a mix of energy sources to keep the supply reliable, provide subsidies and low-interest loans for electric cookstoves and vehicles, and further support private investment through partnerships and feed-in tariffs. The government can't handle the full cost alone, so private help is key. Additional business models such as Build-Own-Operate (BOO) and Build-Own-Transfer (BOT) for public/private partnerships are imperative.

Future work to strengthen the model will focus on refining the data to improve accuracy, as well as integrating the model with other public policy recommendations, CLEWs framework to enhance the climate, water and land analysis. Additionally, the inclusion of social indicators will help ensure that the assessment captures the broader impacts on society and supports more inclusive policy development.

6. References

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